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PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN
WORKING WITH NEW GENERATION TEXTBOOKS.

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Abstract. This article describes the development methods and methodology of the methodology of improving the professional competence of primary school teachers through new generation textbooks, as well as information about the professional skills of primary school teachers through modern textbooks.

Key words: professional competence, pedagogical skill, modern textbook, thinking ability, modern technology, computer, educational goals.

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ
КЛАССОВ РАБОТЕ С УЧЕБНИКАМИ НОВОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ.

Аннотация. В статье описаны методы и методика развития профессиональной компетентности учителей начальных классов с помощью учебников нового поколения, а также информация о профессиональных навыках учителей начальных классов с помощью современных учебников.

Ключевые слова: профессиональная компетентность, педагогическое мастерство, современный учебник, мыслительная способность, современные технологии, компьютер, образовательные цели.

Today, a future primary school teacher should teach primary school students to develop their intellectual thinking potential, intellectual development, their own language skills, self-awareness potential, to feel the beauty of material existence, to understand other people's thoughts, to express their personal thoughts verbally and in writing. It is considered necessary to achieve the formation of feelings of achievement. Also, the use of modern information technologies has a strong influence on keeping up with the times of students today.

The future elementary school teacher should develop the intellectual thinking potential, mental development, self-awareness potential of primary education students, teach them to feel the beauty of material existence, understand the thoughts of others, and achieve the ability to express their personal thoughts verbally and in writing.

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Along with the material factors in the modern organization of the quality of education, improving the effectiveness of improvement, the issue of improving the methodical preparation of future primary school teachers for the intellectual development of students is gaining urgent importance. Because, improving the methodical preparation of future elementary school teachers for the intellectual development of students requires the training of future generation personnel in accordance with the requirements of today's era.

It is important to approach the improvement of methodical training of future elementary school teachers based on the requirements of the time. In order to increase the methodical training of teachers, to form in them the necessary pedagogical knowledge (teacher's work, characteristics of his pedagogical activity, communication, psychology of personality, mental development of students, their age characteristics), skills (behavior performed at a sufficiently high level). must

The analysis of scientific literature showed that in modern psycho-pedagogical science, two independent directions of research are distinguished: the psychology of the teacher of intellectually developed schoolchildren and the preparation of the teacher to work with intellectually developed students.

G.L. Lukankin supports the idea that methodical training of a future primary school teacher should be practically oriented. In this regard, the scientist notes that in solving the issue of primary school teacher training, it is not necessary to increase the number of subjects studied by students, but to individualize the effective organization of education and independent work of the future teacher, that is, it is necessary to strengthen the individual approach from mass, general education [8]. Sh. In his scientific works, S. Sharipov emphasizes that it is important to prepare future primary school teachers for professional activities in a creative information environment, and methodologically trained teachers will be innovative and flexible to new directions of education policy. In his scientific work, the scientist put forward the idea that the student should be taught not how to teach, but how to study[12]. In her research work, N.L.Stefanova explained the content of methodical training of students - future teachers of mathematics. In the opinion of the author, it should include not only knowledge of the academic subject, but also various types of activities in which this knowledge is applied.

It is known from the above comments that the development of the professional competence of the primary school teacher in the context of new textbooks is an important process. Also, today it is very important to organize innovative classes based on modern technologies in the educational process. The use of modern information technologies in the educational process not only teaches students to be independent, but also gives them the opportunity to search for and independently

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study the knowledge they are learning, draw conclusions and analyze it. In such a pedagogical process, the teacher should pay attention to the educational and educational importance of technologies for the education of students as well-rounded individuals. The above considerations, in turn, will be effective in training future primary school teachers to improve their methodical training and train students with a modern approach. Paying special attention to interdisciplinary integration is a very important process in improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers.

The tasks of future primary school teachers in the process of teaching subjects are as follows:

- science should encourage the student to think;
- it is important to be able to learn to understand the thoughts of others;
- to be able to express one's opinion fluently orally and in writing;
- it is necessary to be competent in terms of educational philosophy and history and to be able to comment on the concepts of knowledge, skills, and competences strengthened within the scope of science. The formation of these tasks by primary school teachers will directly affect the development of educated and intellectually developed students in the future.

The teacher's professional skills are determined by the level and method of mastering various types of pedagogical activities. Therefore, the psychological basis of improving the methodological and mathematical skills of the future teacher is an activity-based approach to learning with the division of activities of the teacher and students. Activities in the work program include:

- 1) educational goals (expressed in students' actions),
- 2) educational content, including educational and methodological tasks to form the skills to perform appropriate actions to solve them
- 3) the educational process, its main structural unit is the solution of educational tasks. The development of the teacher is determined by the increase in his level of knowledge. A differential approach to teaching students is determined by the levels of mastering any unit of information: level 1 (understood, memorized, repeated) - minimum; 2nd stage (learned and used in the standard situation) - mandatory; Level 3 (accustomed to a non-standard situation) - the level of opportunities; Level 4 (solved a non-standard problem) - creative.

The choice of the teaching method is a very important and important process, the organization of the lesson through modern information technologies, the use of modern information tools (computer, vice-rector...) is not considered a process that does not always ensure

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the passing of the lesson at an excellent level. But it does not mean that the lesson will not be effective without these tools, if the elementary school teacher chooses the teaching method correctly, it is possible to organize an effective lesson with one simple lesson and chalk. A primary school teacher should be able to organize a lesson using the resources available to him.

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